

Effect of temperature on glycopolymer and Con A binding properties

Jichuan Chen, Roberto Terracciano, Jonas Becker, Gokhan Yilmaz*, C. Remzi Becer*

Department of Chemistry, University of Warwick, Coventry CV4 7AL, United Kingdom

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Glycopolymer
Lectin-carbohydrate interaction
Temperature affect
Turbidimetry assay
Inhibitory potency assay

ABSTRACT

Glycopolymers, a type of synthetic polymer featuring attached carbohydrate components, have emerged as an advanced avenue for different types of biological applications. Their promise stems from their ability to engage in lectin-carbohydrate interactions with specific proteins. In this study, 8 distinct glycopolymers in terms of sugar number, chain length and responsive unit were prepared via Reversible Addition Fragmentation Chain Transfer (RAFT) polymerization. By conducting aggregation, reverse aggregation, and inhibitory potency assays across a temperature range of 10 to 60 °C, we explored how these parameters influence lectin-carbohydrate interactions in relation to temperature. *N,N*-dimethylacrylamide (DMA) and *N*-isopropylacrylamide (NIPAM) were used as a second monomer to synthesize random and block copolymers due to their hydrophilicity and thermal responsive behaviour, respectively. The binding results showed that while all glycopolymers showed faster binding properties at higher temperatures, there was a notable and more significant increase in the case of block copolymers (P4 and P5) compared to the other glycopolymers. Additionally, the obtained MIC₅₀ values from inhibitory potency assay proved that all glycopolymers exhibited greater effectiveness as inhibitors of Concanavalin A (Con A) at elevated temperatures.

1. Introduction

Glycopolymers represent a highly promising approach for the development of targeted delivery systems in biomedical applications with significant potential [1,2]. Glycans play a crucial role as complementary receptors in a variety of interactions in human cells and are furthermore expressed on the surface of cancer cells [3,4]. Glycans bear a specific sugar code, enabling specific interactions to carbohydrate-binding proteins (lectins). One of the concepts of studying these interactions is by mimicking them with well-defined glycopolymers [5,6]. The combination of advanced living polymerization techniques and post-modification approaches in the synthesis of precision glycopolymer makes it possible to produce accurately engineered artificial glycans [7].

Synthetic glycopolymers with controlled molecular structures have found extensive applications in the fields of biomedicine, immunology, and vaccines [8]. In particular, RNA vaccines are one of the most novel and exciting therapeutic approaches after the COVID-19 outbreak [9]. However, nucleic acids are susceptible to degradation by nucleases *in vivo*, leading to reduced targeting efficiency. Utilizing glycopolymer-based targeted delivery of RNA vaccines can offer a solution to the stability issues of nucleic acids *in vivo* by directing them to specific sites [10,11].

Lectins that are a diverse group of glycoproteins could selectively bind to specific carbohydrate structures. They can be present on a wide array of surfaces, including cell membranes, proteins, and various molecules within organisms, spanning across plants, animals, and microorganisms. Importantly, lectins serve a multitude of functions, encompassing cell-cell recognition, cellular adhesion, sorting of glycoproteins, and modulation of immune responses [12]. Lectin-carbohydrate interactions play crucial roles in these biological processes and these specific carbohydrate structures are usually present on the surfaces of cells, glycoproteins, glycolipids, and other biomolecules [13]. Con A is the most widely used and most abundantly available plant lectin. It has high binding affinity with mannose and glucose, making it a commonly chosen model lectin for studying the multivalent binding of glycopolymers. Originally derived from the jack bean, Con A falls within the molecular weight range of 104–112 kDa. Like many other lectins, Con A exhibits binding capabilities with metallic ions such as Mn⁺² and Ca⁺², and these cations notably enhance its affinity for carbohydrates. The most used and long-standing method is turbidimetry, which relies on measuring the solution's turbidity as a result of lectin and polymer chain aggregation. To determine the solution's turbidity at different ratios of lectin to glycopolymers, a UV-vis spectrometer can be employed.

* Corresponding authors.

E-mail addresses: Gokhan.Yilmaz.1@warwick.ac.uk (G. Yilmaz), Remzi.Becer@warwick.ac.uk (C.R. Becer).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2024.113006>

Received 25 January 2024; Received in revised form 29 March 2024; Accepted 30 March 2024

Available online 30 March 2024

0014-3057/© 2024 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

The binding mechanism of lectin-carbohydrate interactions involves a combination of multiple non-covalent interactions between specific amino acid residues on the lectin and functional groups on the carbohydrate molecule. These interactions contribute to the high specificity and reversible nature of lectin-carbohydrate interactions [14]. In particular, the temperature impact on lectin-carbohydrate interactions can have significant effect in biomedical applications [15,16,17]. Therefore, gaining insights into the impact of temperature on these interactions can advance the progress of diverse therapeutic and diagnostic approaches [18,19]. While extensive research has been dedicated to exploring glycopolymer-lectin binding, only a few studies have addressed the influence of temperature on the interaction between lectins and glycopolymers.

Zhu et al. synthesized a set of thermoresponsive double hydrophilic block glycopolymers through RAFT polymerization by using glucose-substituted monomers and NIPAM [20]. The temperature effect on the binding properties with Con A was investigated at 30°C and 37°C. In another study, a series of triblock thermoresponsive polymers with adamantane was synthesized by RAFT. Subsequently, cyclodextrin (CD) functionalized with mannose was incorporated to these polymers via host-guest interaction [21]. The interaction of these glycopolymers with Con A was investigated at 12 °C and 40 °C. The results showed a significant difference between these temperatures in turbidity assay.

Du Prez and collaborators fabricated stimuli-responsive hyper-branched glycopolymers by Cu(0)-mediated polymerization, which was connected by redox-responsive disulfide bonds to form the skeleton and functionalize mannose units at each branching point [22]. The influence of both the polymer concentration and different chain conformations below and above the cloud point was investigated with Con A. Additionally, thermosensitive glucose-functionalized glycopolymers grafted gold nanoparticles were created by RAFT mediated one-pot synthesis [23]. Glycopolymer grafted nanoparticles represented good colloidal stability and thermal sensitivity due to di(ethylene glycol) methyl ether methacrylate (DEGMA) block in aqueous solution. The recognition capabilities of these gold nanoparticles were evaluated using Con A. The results showed that the glycopolymer-grafted nanoparticles exhibited better recognition ability at 37°C compared to 25 °C. This enhancement can be attributed to the DEGMA block becoming more hydrophobic and adhering closely to the gold surface, thereby exposing a greater number of glucose moieties with increased flexibility.

Even though these studies have made significant contributions to a comprehension of the influence of temperature on lectin-carbohydrate interactions, there is still considerable scope for further investigation, particularly regarding a broad of temperature variations and a comparison of both thermally sensitive and non-sensitive glycopolymers. Hence, we aimed to explore the effect of temperature on glycopolymer and Con A binding properties at 6 different temperatures from 10 to 60 °C. 8 distinct glycopolymers in terms of sugar number, chain length and responsive unit (DMA and NIPAM) were synthesized via RAFT successfully. (Table 1) Turbidity assay, reverse aggregation assay and inhibitory potency assay were carried out by using UV-Vis spectroscopy. The binding measurements demonstrated that, with increasing temperatures, all glycopolymers exhibited accelerated binding properties. Notably, block co-glycopolymers (P4 and P5) displayed a more pronounced increase compared to the other glycopolymers. Furthermore, the MIC₅₀ values obtained from the inhibitory potency assay confirmed that all glycopolymers proved to be more effective as Con A inhibitors at higher temperatures.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials

N,N-dimethylacrylamide (DMA, 99 %, contains 250 ppm mono methyl ether hydroquinone (MEHQ) as inhibitor), *N*-hydroxyethyl acrylamide (97 %, contains 1000 ppm MEHQ as inhibitor), *N*-

Table 1

The list of the synthesized glycopolymers.

Polymer code	Structure	DP	Sugar units	M _n Theo (g/mol)	M _n GPC (g/mol)	<i>D</i>
P1	P(ManAm) ₃₀	30	30	12,030	7080	1.15
P2	P(ManAm) _{10-r} -(NIPAM) ₂₀	30	10	6230	3610	1.27
P3	P(ManAm) _{10-r} -(DMA) ₂₀	30	10	6510	5510	1.10
P4	P(ManAm) _{10-b} -(NIPAM) ₂₀	30	10	6230	2560	1.57
P5	P(ManAm) _{10-b} -(DMA) ₂₀	30	10	6510	6000	1.18
P6	P(ManAm) _{10-r} -(NIPAM) _{10-r} -(DMA) ₁₀	30	10	6370	5750	1.22
P7	P(ManAm) _{30-r} -(NIPAM) ₆₀	90	30	18,820	11,020	1.17
P8	P(ManAm) _{30-r} -(DMA) ₆₀	90	30	17,980	7650	1.38

isopropylacrylamide (NIPAM, ≥99 %, contains 250 ppm mono methyl ether hydroquinone (MEHQ) as inhibitor), D-(+)-mannose (≥99 %), sodium methoxide (CH₃ONa, 25 wt% in methanol), boron trifluoride diethyl etherate (BF₃OEt₂, 99 %) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Chemical Co. (Dorset, UK). The RAFT agent, 2-((Butylsulfanyl)carbothioyl)sulfanylpropanoic acid, (PABTC) was purchased from Boron Molecular and dimethyl 2,2'-azobis(2-methylpropanoate) (V601) was kindly provided by Lubrizol. Concanavalin A (Con A) was also purchased Sigma-Aldrich Chemical Co. (Dorset, U.K.). All other reagents and solvents were obtained at the highest purity available from Sigma-Aldrich Chemical Co. (Dorset, U.K.) and used as received unless stated otherwise. Dialysis tubes were purchased from Spectrum Laboratories (California, USA).

2.2. Analytical methods

UV-Vis (Agilent Technologies Cary 3500 UV-Vis Engine) was used for Turbidimetry Assay, Inhibitory Potency Assay, Thermodynamic analysis, Dynamic light scattering (DLS, WYATT technology DynaPro Plate Reader III) was used to analyze self-assembly of block glycopolymers in buffer solution. ¹H NMR (Bruker Avance-400, CDCl₃, D₂O) was used to monitor the conversion of polymerizations and characterize the final structure of the synthesized reagents and polymers: THF and Aqueous Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC, Agilent Technologies 1260 Infinity) were used to characterize the polymers. The THF GPC was calibrated with linear poly(methyl methacrylate) standards in range of 550 to 46890 g·mol⁻¹. All samples were passed through 0.2 μm PTFE filter before analysis. The Aqueous GPC was calibrated with linear polyethylene glycol/oxide standards in range of 20,000 to 1,000,000 g·mol⁻¹.

2.3. Synthesis

Synthesis of Mannose Acrylamide (ManAm): D-Mannose pentaacetate (13.4 g, 0.034 mol) and *N*-hydroxyethyl acrylamide (4.44 g, 0.038 mol) were dissolved in anhydrous dichloromethane (50 mL) and then degassed by argon gas for 20 min. Subsequently, boron trifluoride diethyl etherate (17.20 g, 0.12 mol) was added via syringe and the solution was sonicated for 90 min. The reaction solution was washed with brine for 3 times (30 mL). After the organic layer was dried over MgSO₄, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure to obtain a yellowish gummy crude product. The obtained crude product was purified by column chromatography (chloroform/MeOH, 9:1) to yield a pale amorphous solid (2.13 g, yield: 39.8 %).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, d): 1.99 (s, 3H), 2.01 (s, 6H), 2.07 (s, 3H), 3.66–3.72 (m, 2H), 3.77–3.84 (m, 1H), 4.08–4.15 (m, 2H), 4.27–4.31 (m, 2H), 5.56

(d, 1H), 4.93–5.03 (m, 1H), 5.03–5.11 (m, 2H), 5.15–5.23 (m, 1H), 5.80–5.90 (m, 1H), 6.01–6.20 (m, 1H), 6.36–6.45 (m, 1H).

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, d): 20.56, 20.57 (2C), 20.69, 61.47, 63.14, 67.46, 68.31, 71.08, 71.88, 72.70, 100.8, 128.1, 131.3, 165.9, 169.2, 169.4, 170.3, 170.7.

Synthesis of Homopolymers: The RAFT agent, (PABTC, 1 equiv, 0.17 mmol), monomer (30 equiv, 5 mmol), V601 (0.01 equiv, 0.0017), and dioxane (2 mL) were introduced into a microwave vial equipped with a magnetic stirrer and sealed with a septum. The reaction solution was gently degassed with nitrogen for 30 min, and the mixed solution was allowed to polymerize in oil bath at 70 °C. After confirming of nearly full conversion according to ¹H NMR, the polymerization reaction was stopped by cooling down and exposure to air. Subsequently, the polymer was precipitated in cold diethyl ether twice before characterization by ¹H NMR and THF GPC.

Synthesis of Random Glycopolymers: The RAFT agent, (PABTC, 1 equiv, 0.25 mmol), glycomonomer (10 equiv, 2.5 mmol), NIPAM or DMA (20 equiv, 5 mmol), V601 (0.01 equiv, 0.0025 mmol), and dioxane (2 mL) were introduced into a microwave vial equipped with a magnetic stirrer and sealed with a septum. The reaction solution was gently degassed with nitrogen for 30 min, and the mixed solution was allowed to polymerize in oil bath at 70 °C. After reaching full conversion according to ¹H NMR, the polymerization reaction was stopped by cooling down and exposure to air. Subsequently, the polymer was precipitated in cold diethyl ether twice before characterization by ¹H NMR and THF GPC.

2.4. Synthesis of block glycopolymers

The RAFT agent, (PABTC, 1 equiv, 0.5 mmol), monomer (10 equiv, 5 mmol), V601 (0.01 equiv, 0.005 mmol), and dioxane (2 mL) were introduced into a microwave vial equipped with a magnetic stirrer and sealed with a septum. The reaction solution was gently degassed by nitrogen for 30 min, and the mixed solution was allowed to polymerize in oil bath at 70 °C. After the confirmation of full conversion according to ¹H NMR, second monomer that (20 equiv, 10 mmol in 1 mL) was degassed with nitrogen for 30 min before it was introduced into the microwave vial using a degassed syringe. After assessing the conversion of second block by ¹H NMR, the polymerization reaction was stopped by cooling down and exposure to air. Subsequently, the polymer was precipitated in cold diethyl ether twice before characterization by ¹H NMR and THF GPC.

Deprotection of the synthesized acetyl-protected glycopolymers: The obtained protected glycopolymers (100–150 mg) were dissolved in 5 mL of MeOH. 1 mL of a 2.0 M sodium methoxide solution was added to the solution and the reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h. After the removal of MeOH *via* rotary evaporator, the obtained polymer was re-dissolved in water and neutralized with diluted HCl solution. Subsequently, the mixture was directly transferred to one dialysis tubing and dialyzed against water for 3 days after which the glycopolymer could be recovered by freeze drying. The obtained glycopolymers were characterized by ¹H NMR and Aqueous GPC.

Turbidimetry Assay: The HBS buffer solution (0.10 M HEPES, 0.9 M NaCl, 1 mM MgCl₂, 1 mM CaCl₂, and 1 mM MnCl₂) was prepared for binding experiments. It was adjusted to pH 7.4 and filtered with 0.2 μm regenerated cellulose syringe filter. A fresh solution of 40 mM ConA in HBS buffer solution was prepared before each assay. Turbidity measurements were performed by adding 500 μL of the Con A solution to a 500 μL of polymer solution at various temperatures. The final concentrations of glycopolymers were 120 mM and 360 mM after the addition of Con A solution. The Con A solution was added into the cuvette *via* a pipette, and the absorbance of the mixture was promptly recorded at 420 nm every 0.12 s for 15 min. Every experiment was repeated 3 times.

Reverse Aggregation Assay: This experiment was extended following the aggregation experiment. 0.1 mL of HBS solution containing methyl-α-D-mannopyranoside (αMeMan, 5400 mM) was added, and

the absorbance was recorded over 10 min at various temperatures. The reverse aggregation value's absorbance, determined as 100*(Abs₀-Abs₁₅)/Abs₀, was obtained by calculating the 10 min average UV absorbance at the beginning and end of the reverse aggregation assay. Each experiment was replicated 3 times.

Inhibitory Potency Assay: In the same cuvette, 0.75 mL of glycopolymer solution in HBS (120 mM or 360 mM) was combined with 0.05 mL of αMeMan solution at various concentrations (20 mM, 200 mM, 1400 mM, 2100 mM, 3400 mM, 4200 mM, 6800 mM, 9600 mM, 20,000 mM concerning a total volume of 1 mL for each experiment). Con A solution was introduced into the glycopolymer/αMeMan cuvette, and UV absorbance was observed for 10 min at different temperatures. The UV absorbance concerning the different concentrations of αMeMan for each temperature was plotted to determine MIC₅₀ values.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Synthesis of glycopolymers

RAFT polymerization was performed to prepare all glycopolymers by using protected ManAm, NIPAM and DMA in the presence of PABTC and V-601 as the RAFT agent and the initiator, respectively. The polymerization was carried out in dioxane at 70 °C. The [CTA]₀/[V-601]₀ ratio was set at 10:1 to prevent dead-end polymerization, which is a scenario where all initiators are consumed before achieving complete conversion.

In order to distinguish between thermoresponsive and nonresponsive glycopolymers, DMA and NIPAM were selected for polymerization with ManAm (Scheme 1). This choice was based on DMA's hydrophilic nature and NIPAM's thermal responsiveness. As poly(NIPAM) undergoes a reversible phase transition from hydrophilic to hydrophobic when their solution temperature is raised above their lower critical solution temperature (LCST), changing from an extended chain conformation below LCST into a collapsed chain above LCST. In general, aqueous solutions of poly(NIPAM) exhibit LCST behaviour around 32 °C.

As depicted in Fig. 1, THF GPC was initially used after each polymerization, and the results revealed monomodal distributions with a clear shift to higher molecular weights after each monomer addition. All polymerizations have been achieved with a good control due to a narrow dispersity index with high molar mass. Following the deprotection of acetyl groups in the presence of sodium methoxide (CH₃ONa) in methanol (MeOH), aqueous GPC analysis based on poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) standards indicated that some glycopolymers showed a small amount of shoulder at high molecular weight, even though they had a single peak in THF GPC. The possible reason of that could be an interaction of mannose moieties of the polymers and SEC column packing materials or some coupling reactions during the deprotection reaction. The conversion values of monomers were calculated using ¹H NMR *via* the vinyl protons of monomers at 5.8–6.2 ppm. The ¹H NMR analysis revealed that quantitative conversions were achieved for each monomer. The Mn by GPC is slightly higher or lower than the theoretical molar mass mainly due to the different structure of the obtained polymers according to due to the different structures of the synthesized polymers and the calibration standard polymer. The theoretical number average molar masses of the synthesized polymers, Mn_(Theo), was calculated by using the equation (Mn_(Theo) = ([M]₀/[RAFT]₀ × conversion × M_{mon}) + M_{RAFT}) where [RAFT]₀ is the initial RAFT concentration, [M]₀ is the initial monomer concentration, M_{mon} is the monomer molecular weight and M_{RAFT} is the RAFT agent's molecular weight.

4. The effect of temperature on Con A binding

4.1. The effect of temperature on aggregation binding assay

The investigation of the binding ability of the synthesized glycopolymers at different temperatures was carried out in the presence of Con A. Plant lectins are widely employed in the study of multivalent

Fig. 1. (A) ^1H NMR spectrum of the synthesized **P4** in D_2O ; (B) THF GPC traces of the first and second blocks of **P4**; (C) Aqueous GPC trace of **P4** after the deprotection.

carbohydrate binding, given their pivotal roles in both the external and internal processes of plants. Con A, which forms a tetramer with four subunits at a neutral pH, exhibits a strong binding affinity for mannose and glucose. Therefore, Con A is commonly utilized as a model lectin for investigating the multivalent binding interactions of glycopolymers due to its low price and stability at different temperatures. The UV-vis spectrometer serves as a straightforward and adaptable instrument for assessing solution turbidity across different ratios of lectin to glycopolymers. Turbidimetry assay is to measure the loss of intensity of transmitted light due to the scattering effect of suspended in the solution. Con A was dissolved in the filtered HBS buffer (20 mM) and then transferred into a dry 1.5 mL cuvette. The cuvette was placed in the UV spectrometer. A solution of the glycopolymers in HBS buffer (120 mM and 360 mM) was added into solution and then the absorbance of the mixture was quickly recorded at 420 nm for 15 min every 0.12 s. A linear fit to the initial part of the curve was used to determine the rate of the clustering (K_{on}), which was expressed as arbitrary units per minute (AU/min). The endpoint of the curve was used to calculate the time for half-maximal precipitation ($t_{1/2}$) of Con A.

In general, all glycopolymers represented rapid binding properties at higher temperatures according to an increase in initial binding rates and a decrease in time values for half-maximal precipitation (Figs. 2 and 3). **P2** consistently exhibited a higher aggregation ratio in comparison to **P3**. Notably, the trend of increased aggregation ratio for **P2** began at 40 °C, surpassing that of **P3**. This phenomenon is attributed to the influence of the LCST of NIPAM. Additionally, two random copolymers with a lower sugar unit content in the polymer chain showed significantly higher aggregation ratios compared to **P1**. This observation suggests that random copolymers involving NIPAM or DMA with ManAm enhance the binding efficiency of mannose with Con A. However, these random copolymers with the same sugar concentration (360 mM) exhibited considerably higher initial binding rates after at 40, 50 and 60 °C. This difference reached approximately threefold at 40 °C and nine-fold at 50 °C. The reason being of this could be that higher glycopolymer concentration increases multivalency of glycopolymer for Con A binding even though the amount of sugar unit was the same [24,25]. In particular, the initial aggregation ratio of **P2** and **P3** is 9 times higher than **P1** at 50 °C although sugar concentration was the same in each solution, which confirms that not only sugar concentration, but also polymer concentration emphasized the influence of temperature on the lectin-carbohydrate interactions.

The results of the inhibitory potency assay also proved this phenomenon due to that the Con A cluster with **P2** required a higher concentration of α MeMan to achieve a 50 % reduction in UV absorbance compared to other glycopolymer/Con A clusters. In contrast, the MIC₅₀ value for **P3** remained nearly identical to that of **P1**.

P6 that is the random copolymer of all monomers showed a higher aggregation ratio compared with **P2**. The trend of growth for the aggregation ratio of **P6** also showed higher from 40 °C compared with **P2**, which was considered as the presence of DMA in the polymer chain

Fig. 2. The results of turbidimetry assay for the initial rate of the clustering of glycopolymers with Con A at different temperatures.

Fig. 3. The time for half-maximal precipitation results of turbidimetry assay of clustering of glycopolymers with Con A.

amplified the influence of NIPAM to the lectin-carbohydrate interactions. For the equivalent sugar concentration, **P6** exhibited a reduced aggregation ratio when compared to both **P1** and **P2**. This was in contrast to the situation at lower concentrations, where **P6** showed a slightly lower aggregation ratio than **P1** and **P2** at 60 °C. This observation can be attributed to that **P6** is more sensitive to variations in concentration, which limits the impact of NIPAM. Consequently, its behaviour tends to align more closely with that of **P3**.

P4 ($P(\text{ManAm})_{10}\text{-}b\text{-}(\text{NIPAM})_{20}$) always showed a significantly higher aggregation ratio after 30 °C compared with **P2** ($P(\text{ManAm})_{10}\text{-}r\text{-}(\text{NIPAM})_{20}$), which was around 11 times higher at 40 °C. However, the aggregation ratio of **P4** was almost the same with **P2** at lower than 40 °C. This was considered as the influence of LCST for NIPAM was amplified by the block copolymer structure and built up a significantly high clustering efficiency. Moreover, **P4**, featuring one-third the quantity of sugar units in its polymer chain, exhibited a 15-fold increase in aggregation ratio compared to **P1** at 40 °C and a tenfold increase at 50 °C. This signifies that the block copolymer of NIPAM with ManAm significantly enhanced the efficiency of mannose binding to Con A. At the same sugar concentration, two NIPAM/ManAm copolymers displayed a similar aggregation ratio within the temperature range of 10 to 30 °C. However, a distinction emerged at 40 °C, with the ratio increasing for the random copolymer (**P2**) while remaining relatively constant for the block copolymer (**P4**). This contrasted with the behaviour at lower concentrations, where the ratio began to rise at 40 °C within a 120 mM solution. Subsequently, the aggregation ratio for **P4** surged by 100-fold from 40 to 50 °C. This outcome suggests that increased concentration affects the

molecule's mobility and influences lectin-carbohydrate interactions with an increase in temperature.

At 50 and 60 °C, the disparity between the random copolymer and block copolymer diminished, confirming that at elevated temperatures, the structural influence of the copolymers can become constrained. The DLS analysis results revealed the formation of micelles by **P4** at 37 °C with a concentration of 5 mg/ml, which further indicates that the aggregation and reversion dynamics observed in **P4** may also be influenced by self-assembly processes.

The comparison between **P1**, **P2**, and **P7** pertains to the degree of polymerization at varying temperatures. At an equivalent molecular concentration, **P7** exhibited higher aggregation ratios beyond 30 °C in contrast to **P1** and **P2**. This increase in K_{on} values can be attributed to the combined effect of a greater quantity of sugar units and a higher number of NIPAM units in **P7**. Despite having a 3-fold increase in degree of polymerization for both monomers, the aggregation ratio only doubled, suggesting that the contribution to aggregation efficiency was somewhat restricted.

P5 which is the block copolymer with DMA always showed significantly higher aggregation ratios than **P3** at elevated temperatures, roughly 10-fold higher, though still less than that of **P4**. This effect can be attributed to the block copolymer's structure, which enhances clustering efficiency. **P5**, characterized by one-third the quantity of sugar units in its polymer chain, displayed a 12-fold increase in aggregation ratio compared to **P1** at 40 °C and a 13-fold increase at 50 °C. These results showed that the block copolymer composed of DMA and ManAm significantly enhances the binding ability of mannose to Con A. **P8**, at an equivalent molecular concentration, exhibited a reduced aggregation ratio from 10 to 40 °C compared to **P3** at 120 mM. Similarly, it displayed a lower aggregation ratio from 10 to 50 °C compared to **P3** at 360 mM, eventually reaching the same level at 60 °C. This observation suggests that higher temperatures have a notable impact on the longer glycopolymers' binding properties.

Overall, all glycopolymers promoted the precipitation very rapidly ($t_{1/2} < 2$ s) at 50 and 60 °C, which is significantly faster than lower temperatures. Evidently, the precipitation of Con A with **P8** was very slow at 10 and 20 °C ($t_{1/2} \geq 87$ s).

4.2. The effect of temperature on reversible aggregation binding assay

As the interaction between lectin and carbohydrate is reversible, the stability of the complexes formed by glycopolymer and Con A were evaluated *via* reverse aggregation assay. By addition of monovalent ligand α MeMan at 5400 mM into the turbidity solution, the rate of the reverse interaction was determined by a linear fit of the steepest portion of the data (K_{off}) (Fig. 4). As depicted in Fig. 5, the percent change of the turbidity after 10 min was calculated using $[A_{420}(t = 0) - A_{420}(t = 10)] / A_{420}(t = 0)$.

Each glycopolymer was very stable and the reverse interaction was very slow at lower temperatures, however, there was a significant

Fig. 4. The calculated K_{off} values *via* reversible aggregation binding assay at different temperatures.

Fig. 5. The results of turbidimetry assay for the $100 \cdot (Abs_0 - Abs_{15}) / Abs_0$ of de-clustering of glycopolymers with Con A at different temperatures.

decrease in the stability of glycopolymer-Con A clusters after 30 °C due to quick interaction between α MeMan and ConA. The turbidity almost disappeared after couples of seconds at elevated temperatures.

P2 exhibited a better stability in comparison to **P3**. The trend in the increase of the reverse aggregation ratio for **P2** was notably more pronounced from at higher temperature, while **P3** showed a nearly consistent trend. This difference could be caused by LCST effect of NIPAM. Moreover, **P2** consistently had a lower ratio compared to **P1** and **P3**. This result revealed that the presence of NIPAM strengthened the lectin-carbohydrate interactions with Con A, even with fewer mannose units, while the presence of DMA weakened these interactions, making it easier for α MeMan to replace glycopolymers from Con A. At the same sugar concentration, **P2** had a significantly lower ratio compared to **P1**, indicating much stronger lectin-carbohydrate interactions. This difference was roughly half at 10 °C and 10-fold at 60 °C. In contrast, the ratio for **P3** did not exhibit a substantial difference compared to **P1**, suggesting that the presence of DMA did not significantly influence the lectin-carbohydrate interactions, whereas the presence of NIPAM contributed significantly to the strength of these interactions.

P6 showed a lower reverse aggregation ratio compared with **P2**, leading to relatively stronger lectin-carbohydrate interactions. The trend of growth for the reverse aggregation ratio of **P6** did not show a significant change with the rise of temperature below 40 °C, also indicating the influence of LCST for NIPAM. At the same sugar concentration, **P6** did not show as good stability as **P2**, but it was still diminished compared to its own performance at 120 mM, with a maximum of approximately 60 % at 60 °C. The growth of the ratio still showed a trend change with the increase of temperature after 30 °C, this was considered as the influence of NIPAM. $100 \cdot (Abs_0 - Abs_{15}) / Abs_0$ also showed a higher percentage of reverse aggregation compared with **P2**, which lead to weaker lectin-carbohydrate interactions.

P4 showed a much higher reverse aggregation ratio than **P2** and **P1**, as 3 times larger than **P2** on 10 °C, 9 times larger on 30 °C and 14 times larger on 60 °C. This indicated that the block glycopolymer of NIPAM results in significantly weaker lectin-carbohydrate interactions, leading to a high binding efficiency but fragile lectin-carbohydrate interactions. The trend of the stability of **P4** represented a considerable change with the rise of temperature at 10, 20 and 30 °C, also indicating the influence of LCST for NIPAM.

Even though **P7** showed slower reverse interaction than **P1** and **P2** at between 10 and 40 °C, its K_{off} values raised significantly at 50 °C and 60 °C compared to **P1** and **P2**. This could be explained by that more NIPAM units on the polymer backbone effected lectin-carbohydrate interaction in different way below and beyond LCST. $100 \cdot (Abs_0 - Abs_{15}) / Abs_0$ also showed a low percentage of reverse aggregation for **P7** at lower temperatures. **P5** showed a higher reverse aggregation ratio compared with both **P3** and **P1**, as 3 times higher than **P3** at 10 °C, 3 times higher at 30 °C and 4 times higher at 60 °C, but lower than the difference between **P** (ManAm)₁₀-*r*-(NIPAM)₂₀ and **P** (ManAm)₁₀-*b*-(NIPAM)₂₀. Concentration did not influence much for the reverse aggregation ratio for both random and block copolymer of ManAm/DMA. This indicated much weaker lectin-carbohydrate interactions for the block glycopolymer.

P8 exhibited a discontinuity in the ratio increase between 20 and 30 °C, significantly surpassing **P3** at these temperatures. Additionally, **P8** displayed a decreased reverse aggregation between 40 and 60 °C compared to **P1** and **P3**. This can be attributed to the fact that, even though the lectin-carbohydrate interactions of **P8** were relatively weak, the presence of a sufficient number of mannose units on each chain prevented α MeMan from replacing all glycopolymers from Con A.

4.3. The effect of temperature on inhibitory potency assay

The inhibitory potency of multivalent ligands is a critical determinant of their suitability for use in identifying potent inhibitors. The inhibitory potency assay was performed by adding Con A to the mixture solution of glycopolymer and α MeMan to measure the absorbance at 420 nm of the resulting turbidity. By varying the concentration of α MeMan, the minimum inhibitory concentration for half-maximum precipitation (MIC_{50}) values of α MeMan were determined (Fig. 6).

When comparing the MIC_{50} values of α MeMan for all the glycopolymers, it's clear that the inhibitory potency of each glycopolymer rises with higher temperatures. Notably, **P2** emerged as the most effective inhibitor of Con A across a range of temperatures. At both concentrations, the MIC_{50} of **P4** and **P5** is significantly lower compared to other glycopolymers due to probably their block structures. The minimum inhibitory concentration of Con A by **P6** against α MeMan did not show a considerable change at different temperatures. However, **P7** represented a dramatic increase, especially after 30 °C. Moreover, **P8** showed a significant increase at higher temperature and its MIC_{50} value was the highest one at 60 °C, which is correspond with the result of $100 \cdot (Abs_0 - Abs_{15}) / Abs_0$.

5. Conclusions

In this work, 8 different glycopolymers were synthesized using RAFT polymerization. DMA and NIPAM were used as a second monomer to synthesize random and block copolymers with the glycomonomer due to their hydrophilicity and thermal responsive behaviour, respectively. By conducting aggregation, reverse aggregation and inhibitory potency assays by using UV-Vis spectroscopy at 6 different temperatures from 10 to 60 °C, the effect of the temperature on glycopolymer and Con A interaction was investigated.

Overall, all glycopolymers represented rapid binding properties at higher temperatures according to an increase in initial binding rates and a decrease in time values for half-maximal precipitation. Each glycopolymer was very stable and the reverse interaction was very slow at lower temperatures, however, there was a significant decrease in the

Fig. 6. The MIC_{50} values of α MeMan for all the glycopolymers via inhibitory potency assays at different temperatures.

stability of glycopolymer-Con A clusters after 30 °C due to quick interaction between α MeMan and ConA. All glycopolymers promoted the precipitation very rapidly ($t_{1/2} < 2$ s) at 50 and 60 °C, which is significantly faster than lower temperatures. Evidently, the precipitation of Con A with **P8** was very slow at 10 and 20 °C ($t_{1/2} \geq 87$ s). Interestingly, even though block co-glycopolymers (**P4** and **P5**) displayed a more pronounced increase compared to the other glycopolymers, their inhibitory potency properties were lower than other glycopolymers.

Therefore, the temperature has a significant effect on the binding properties contributed by different clustering parameters, and this effect depends on the nature of the glycopolymer. The obtained results offer potential avenues for designing new glycopolymeric structures tailored for specific applications at varying temperatures, as the interaction between glycopolymer and Con A can be modulated by temperature.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jichuan Chen; **Roberto Terracciano**: Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Jonas Becker**: Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Gokhan Yilmaz**: Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation. **C. Remzi Becer**: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgment

R.T. and J.B. received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no 859416 (BIOMOLMACS).

Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2024.113006>.

References

- [1] M. Bartneck, C.T. Schlößer, M. Barz, R. Zentel, C. Trautwein, T. Lammers, F. Tacke, Immunomodulatory therapy of inflammatory liver disease using selectin-binding glycopolymers, *ACS Nano* 11 (10) (2017) 9689–9700.
- [2] E. de Oliveira Figueiroa, C.R. Albuquerque da Cunha, P. Albuquerque, R.A. de Paula, M.A. Aranda-Souza, M.S. Alves, A. Zagnignan, M.G. Carneiro-da-Cunha, L. C. Nascimento da Silva, M.T. dos Santos Correia, Lectin-carbohydrate interactions: implications for the development of new anticancer agents, *Curr. Med. Chem.* 24 (34) (2017) 3667–3680.
- [3] A. Munoz-Bonilla, J.P. Heuts, M. Fernández-García, Glycoparticles and bioactive films prepared by emulsion polymerization using a well-defined block glycopolymer stabilizer, *Soft Matter* 7 (6) (2011) 2493–2499.
- [4] Y. Miura, Y. Hoshino, H. Seto, Glycopolymer nanobiotechnology, *Chem. Rev.* 116 (4) (2016) 1673–1692.
- [5] S.M. Banik, K. Pedram, S. Wisnovsky, G. Ahn, N.M. Riley, C.R. Bertozzi, Lysosome-targeting chimaeras for degradation of extracellular proteins, *Nature* 584 (7820) (2020) 291–297.
- [6] D. Ponader, F. Wojcik, F. Beceren-Braun, J. Dervede, L. Hartmann, Sequence-defined glycopolymer segments presenting mannose: synthesis and lectin binding affinity, *Biomacromolecules* 13 (6) (2012) 1845–1852.
- [7] Y. Abdouni, G. Yilmaz, C.R. Becer, Sequence controlled polymers from a novel β -cyclodextrin core, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* 38 (24) (2017) 1700501.
- [8] F. Jafari, G. Yilmaz, C.R. Becer, Stimuli-responsive glycopolymers and their biological applications, *Eur. Polym. J.* 142 (2021) 110147.
- [9] M. Tengdelius, D. Gurav, P. Konradsson, P. Pålsson, M. Griffith, O.P. Oommen, Synthesis and anticancer properties of fucoidan-mimetic glycopolymer coated gold nanoparticles, *Chem. Commun.* 51 (40) (2015) 8532–8535.
- [10] C. Lavilla, G. Yilmaz, V. Uzunova, R. Napier, C.R. Becer, A. Heise, Block-sequence-specific glycopolypeptides with selective lectin binding properties, *Biomacromolecules* 18 (6) (2017) 1928–1936.
- [11] T. Zhao, R. Terracciano, J. Becker, A. Monaco, G. Yilmaz, C.R. Becer, Hierarchy of complex Glycomacromolecules: from controlled topologies to biomedical applications, *Biomacromolecules* 23 (3) (2022) 543–575.
- [12] J. Wang, X. Shi, M. Xiong, W.-S. Tan, H. Cai, Trehalose glycopolymers for cryopreservation of tissue-engineered constructs, *Cryobiology* 104 (2022) 47–55.
- [13] S. Cecioni, J.P. Praly, S.E. Matthews, M. Wimmerová, A. Imberty, S. Vidal, Rational design and synthesis of optimized glycoclusters for multivalent lectin-carbohydrate interactions: influence of the linker arm, *Chem.–A Euro. J.* 18 (20) (2012) 6250–6263.
- [14] R. Sunasee, R. Narain, Glycopolymers and glyco-nanoparticles in biomolecular recognition processes and vaccine development, *Macromol. Biosci.* 13 (1) (2013) 9–27.
- [15] X. Zhang, V.K. Yadavalli, Functionalized self-assembled monolayers for measuring single molecule lectin carbohydrate interactions, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 649 (1) (2009) 1–7.
- [16] L.L. Kiessling, J.C. Grim, Glycopolymer probes of signal transduction, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 42 (10) (2013) 4476–4491.
- [17] Y. Liu, J. Lee, K.M. Mansfield, J.H. Ko, S. Sallam, C. Wesdemiotis, H.D. Maynard, Trehalose glycopolymer enhances both solution stability and pharmacokinetics of a therapeutic protein, *Bioconjug. Chem.* 28 (3) (2017) 836–845.
- [18] Y. Wang, R. Narain, Y. Liu, Study of bacterial adhesion on different glycopolymer surfaces by quartz crystal microbalance with dissipation, *Langmuir* 30 (25) (2014) 7377–7387.
- [19] Y. Wang, Y. Kotsuchibashi, Y. Liu, R. Narain, Study of bacterial adhesion on biomimetic temperature responsive glycopolymer surfaces, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 7 (3) (2015) 1652–1661.
- [20] K. Sun, S.A. Bligh, H.-L. Nie, J. Quan, L.-M. Zhu, Lectin recognizing thermoresponsive double hydrophilic glycopolymer micelles by RAFT polymerization, *RSC Adv.* 4 (66) (2014) 34912–34921.
- [21] N. Cakir, G. Hizal, C.R. Becer, Supramolecular glycopolymers with thermoresponsive self-assembly and lectin binding, *Polym. Chem.* 6 (37) (2015) 6623–6631.
- [22] S. Vandewalle, S. Wallyn, S. Chattopadhyay, C.R. Becer, F. Du Prez, Thermoresponsive hyperbranched glycopolymers: Synthesis, characterization and lectin interaction studies, *Eur. Polym. J.* 69 (2015) 490–498.
- [23] F.-W. Shen, K.-C. Zhou, H. Cai, Y.-N. Zhang, Y.-L. Zheng, J. Quan, One-pot synthesis of thermosensitive glycopolymers grafted gold nanoparticles and their lectin recognition, *Colloids Surf. B Biointerfaces* 173 (2019) 504–511.
- [24] T.K. Dam, C.F. Brewer, Multivalent lectin-carbohydrate interactions: energetics and mechanisms of binding, *Adv. Carbohydr. Chem. Biochem.* 63 (2010) 139–164.
- [25] K.J. Neurohr, H.H. Mantsch, N.M. Young, D.R. Bundle, Carbon-13 nuclear magnetic resonance studies on lectin-carbohydrate interactions: binding of specifically carbon-13-labeled methyl. beta.-D-lactoside to peanut agglutinin, *Biochemistry* 21 (3) (1982) 498–503.